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ENERGIZING MOTIVATION FOR TEACHING LEARNING EFFECTIVENESS

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Abstract: This research assessed the teachers' motivational factors under the new normal. The researchers used the descriptive research method to gather information about the respondents' demographic profile. The data obtained were analyzed using percentage weighted mean, and t-test for significant difference on their level of motivation. Based on the findings, data shows that teachers have different needs in this new normal of education from preparation, distribution and retrieval of modules. Moreover, data shows that both respondent groups have perceived that teacher need an immediate help in terms of preparation, distribution and retrieval of modules. Thus, teachers need physical support in fulfilling their job. Results also suggest that there is a need an immediate support for teachers to cater the needs of students and parents, such as time allowance in module distribution and retrieval.

Keywords: Energizing Motivation, Module preparation, Module distribution and module Retrieval

1. Introduction

Today in a world of competitive school environment a motivated employee is crucial in attaining the organizational aims and objectives. They will look at teaching through a different lens, and, in doing so, motivate their students in their learning too. Motivation helps to energize, direct and sustain positive behavior over a long period of time. It involves working towards goals and tailoring activities to achieving this purpose. It also helps to drive creativity and curiosity, sparking the desire needed for employees to be productive.

Galvez (2018) stated that in any organization, motivation plays an important role in shaping behavior. It influences productivity and work performance. It is a need, drive or desire that serves to organize behavior and directs it toward a goal. It makes a person continue his/her activity or work as a human being. According to the reports of the article Smarp (2020) no matter how big or small a company is, employee motivation is always one of the biggest employers' goals. Moreover, prior research has shown that

employee motivation is highly linked with employee engagement. Moreover, employee engagement almost always leads to higher productivity. However, recent research from CV-Library (2020), the UK's leading independent job site, has found that 55% of employees are unhappy at work. Gaile (2017) found out that more than half of the American workforce feels disengaged from their jobs, meaning most workers are not productive and performing with minimal care than the unmotivated counterpart. This statement is irrespective of the kind of motivation under consideration. The reason being that, a motivated teacher is equipped with adequate number of external stimuli for students, while the unmotivated teacher may produce an under stimulated classroom which will consequently yield poor students learning outcomes, in particular, discipline problems. Moreover, it is important to note that a worker's level of motivation cannot be properly measured because psychological processes cannot be directly observed.

Moreover, there exist many constraints which adversely affect goal attainment. Demir & Budak (2016) stated that motivation is a triggering power for learning. The lack of motivation means that there is no action and therefore difficulty in reaching the desired goal (Demir & Budak, 2016). Motivation is an important factor in the effectiveness of learning and teaching processes since it is not only a significant factor in students' achievements but also it gives energy and ensures that behavior is voluntary.

The need to address teacher motivation also derives from teacher shortage reported by many western countries including the US, Australia and some other European countries like the UK, Germany and Norway. A renewed research interest in teachers' motivation to teach and to remain teaching in the past decade has highlighted possible causes of the existing and potential teacher shortages as early teacher attrition, teaching force ageing, imbalance of high demand with less reward, limited career opportunities, less job security and low prestige. The significance of teacher motivation research is also self-evident as it is a crucial factor closely related to a number of variables in education such as student motivation, educational reform, teaching practice and teachers' psychological fulfillment and well-being. Therefore, it is helpful for administrators to determine how to attract potential teachers and how to retain them in teaching. (OECD, 2005).

Furthermore, the work itself is also a contributor to employee motivation. There is a fact that an employee might absolutely love his or her job, is satisfied with the pay, and has good relationships with his/her colleagues, but still finds the work itself completely boring and uninspiring. A happy employee may stay, but if you really want to motivate the employees, create interesting work and let them engage with it. This means forming strong work cultures, encouraging creative thinking and innovation, and especially, avoiding unhealthy, unequal and impotent working environments (Landrum 2015)

Healthfield (2017) stated that whatever the job is and no matter what your position is, it is very important to an employee that his/her efforts are recognized. If an employee has been spending a lot of time working on a task, or is even just willing to help out the other co-workers, give them applause and show them your gratitude. It can be understood that it is not merely about giving praise. If the efforts of an employee are recognized, he/she will feel achievement and fulfillment and continue to excel in the work. However, it is crucial to consider that the recognition as a motivator may differ among employees as one might increase the work productivity after being recognized while one is the opposite. By working closely with employees, you may know how they react to recognition, thus being able to offer a fitting way of appreciation. TCT (2018) emphasized that keeping your teachers motivated can be a challenge. But it is an

essential part of your students' overall success. Great teachers are those that are motivated to excel and take pride in their students' success both inside and outside the classroom this includes publicly praise teachers, encourage teachers to rewards each other, provide opportunities to take breaks, encourage collaboration and empower each other's strength in this way, teachers are well motivated to achieved the school aim and objectives.

Over the last decade, research from many different countries has demonstrated the important role played by teachers in increasing students' learning and improving their academic performance. Studies from countries as different as the US and Indonesia have shown the enormous benefits that follow from having adequate and effective teachers working in a country's schools. In Indonesia, a value-added analysis of student learning outcomes found that the more teachers know, the greater the improvements in the learning competencies of primary and junior secondary students. In the US, better teaching in elementary and secondary schools has been shown to increase students' college participation rates, raise their subsequent earnings, and improve other long-term outcomes. Providing teachers with good quality professional development opportunities has been shown to be an effective way of increasing their competencies and improving student learning outcomes in many different settings. A series of systematic reviews have been undertaken recently to assess the impact of different interventions on student learning outcomes in developing countries. One of the most consistent findings from these reviews has been the positive and significant impact that interventions to strengthen teaching practice, introduce innovative instructional methods, and strengthen teachers' subject knowledge can have on student learning. However, in many countries, such professional development opportunities frequently fail to meet even minimum levels of quality and fall short of what teachers want and need (World Bank Group, 2016).

In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) has issued an order to all of its school heads, supervisors, and teachers for the adoption of "the enclosed Basic Education Research Agenda" which promotes the "conduct of education research" (DepEd, 2016) in the country. The purpose of which is to identify teachers and department's concerns and problems, and to recommend solutions based on the results and findings made. With professional growth and development as one of the key result areas for the individual teacher's performance commitment. However, many teachers in both elementary and secondary schools were uninterested and demotivated. Factors like tight teaching timetable and heavy teaching workload and paper works are just few of the reasons why some public-school teachers are not motivated in finding ways to solve the problem at school (DepEd, 2016).

According to Sterling (2014) teacher motivation has implications not only for the teachers themselves but also for the classroom experiences of students and the overall stability and effectiveness of educational systems. Therefore, it is fundamental to assess what are the determinants of teachers' motivation that make them motivated to continually support them in their journey as an educator. Moreover, when teacher is motivated, they are also keen to teach and motivate learners. According to UNESCO (2018) Improving the motivation and status of teachers generally improves teaching. Research suggests that students learn more in classrooms with highly dedicated and motivated teachers. Therefore, raising the motivation and status of teachers as well as retaining high-quality teachers is therefore vital to improving education. Overall, this study will assess the factors that make teachers productive and motivated. The researcher believes that a motivated teacher is the one who will bring

light and peace in the education system. Hence, this study was conducted to assess the factors that leads to teachers' motivation, as far as basic education is concerned.

2. Purpose of the Study

This research assessed the teachers' motivational factors under the new normal. The status of the implementation of modular based instruction as to: preparation, distribution, retrieval and performance and also the extent of teachers motivational and demotivation factors was considered in the main problem of the study.

3. Research Methodology

The descriptive method of research was used in this study, which described data and the characteristics of the population under study. Together with sets of questionnaires as data gathering instruments. As widely used, descriptive research describes a certain present state. Reasonably, the method is applicable to this study since it aims to describe the current condition. This method answered the questions who, what, where, when, and how. The data gathered used processed and analyzed utilizing the appropriate statistical software utilizing 0.05 level of significance.

4. Results and Discussions

Table 1. Preparation

PREPARATION	Teachers		Administrator	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Extra support in module preparation (e.g., printing and sorting of module)	3.25	MA	3.22	MA
School provides free meals to teachers inside the school.	2.12	D	2.16	D
Video guidance to support in teaching through online class.	2.32	D	2.31	D
Additional printer and bond paper for printing	3.67	A	3.55	A
Provide teachers with personal protective equipment (Masks, face shield, etc.).	3.38	MA	3.40	MA
Social and academic development for teachers was given with ease in times of covid 19 pandemic.	3.54	A	3.48	A
Social and health services given to teachers in module preparation.	2.98	A	2.87	MA
Grand Mean	3.04	MA	3.00	MA

Table 1 shows the data on teachers' preparation. Data shows that teachers received additional printer and bond paper for printing which was rated as the highest weighted mean of 3.67 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to school provides free meals to teachers inside the school got the lowest weighted mean of 2.12 which verbally described as disagree. This indicates that teachers were not provided a free meal when they report to school. On the other hand, administrators' response showed that school gave additional support on teacher's preparation which was also rated the statement additional printer and bon paper as the highest weighted mean of 3.55 which also verbally described as agree. while statement refers to teachers don't receive a free meal at school got also rated as the lowest weighted mean which also verbally described as disagree. This indicates that teachers are at risk in getting covid-19 virus if they will have their meals outside the school.

Table 2. Distribution

DISTRIBUTION	Teachers		Administrator	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Extra support in module distribution (e.g., distribution by subject and section).	3.28	MA	3.22	MA
Provision of two-way communication between teacher, tutor or the learner in addressing learner's performance.	3.16	MA	2.16	D
Connections between teachers and learners in module distribution (un-answered quizzes, no submitted outputs).	2.82	MA	2.89	MA
Establishing proper, continuous person-to-person meetings on a regular basis for learners' performance.	3.12	MA	3.10	MA
School provides vehicle for delivery and retrieval of modules for learners.	3.38	MA	2.43	D
Additional time in distribution of the printed or offline modules.	3.54	A	3.48	MA
Distribution of modules through courier or school service delivery.	2.22	D	2.41	D
Grand Mean	3.07	MA	2.81	MA

Table 2 shows the data on teachers' distribution. Data shows that the statement refers to additional time in distribution of the printed or offline modules got the highest weighted mean of 3.54 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to distribution of modules through courier or school service delivery got the lowest weighted mean of 2.22 which verbally described as disagree. Administrators on the other hand, the statement refers to additional time in distribution of the printed or offline modules got also the highest weighted mean of 3.48 which also verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to distribution of modules through courier or school service delivery got also the lowest weighted mean of 2.41 which verbally described as disagree. This indicates that teachers are manually giving students materials without additional support from the schools.

Table 3. Retrieval

RETRIEVAL	Teachers		Administrator	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Extra support in module retrieval (e.g., retrieval by subject and section).	3.21	MA	3.36	MA
Parents submit modules on time.	3.03	MA	3.21	MA
Additional time in reviewing the materials before accepting it.	2.98	MA	3.16	MA
Additional time for learners to complete their module.	3.02	MA	3.08	MA
Social distancing with compliance with risk-based safety and health protocols practices in module retrieval.	3.18	MA	3.10	MA
Schools provide vehicle for delivery and retrieval of modules for learners.	2.21	D	2.20	D
Schools are enjoined to do a one-time retrieval of modules, including the textbooks and other learning materials.	2.23	D	2.45	D
Grand Mean	2.84	MA	2.94	MA

Table 3 shows the data in terms of retrieval. Data shows that the statement refers to extra support in module retrieval (e.g., retrieval by subject and section) got the highest weighted mean of 3.21 which verbally described as moderately agree, while the

statement refers to schools provide vehicle for delivery and retrieval of modules for learners got the lowest weighted mean of 2.21 which verbally described as disagree. Administrators on the other hand, the statement refers to extra support in module retrieval (e.g., retrieval by subject and section) got also the highest weighted mean of 3.36 which verbally described as moderately agree, while the statement refers to schools provide vehicle for delivery and retrieval of modules for learners got also the lowest weighted mean of 2.20 which verbally described as disagree. This indicates that teachers are manually retrieving the students' materials without additional support from the schools.

Table 4. Performance

PERFORMANCE	Teachers		Administrator	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Government, parents, administrators, and community recognized the hard work of teachers.	3.26	MA	3.29	MA
Learners are doing well on their distance education.	3.01	MA	3.16	MA
Teachers have good performance ratings in time of covid 19 pandemic.	3.25	MA	3.10	MA
Additional incentives given to teachers for being a front liner in this pandemic.	2.88	MA	3.04	MA
Teachers who perform well get rewards and recognition or promotion.	3.12	MA	3.08	MA
Additional hazard pays for teachers and staffs for going to school every day.	2.64	MA	2.72	MA
Grand Mean	3.03	MA	3.07	MA

Table 4 shows the data in terms of performance. Data shows that the statement refers to government, parents, administrators, and community recognized the hard work of teachers got the highest weighted mean for teachers and administrators with a mean of 3.26 and 3.29 which verbally described as moderately agree, while the statement refers to additional hazard pays for teachers and staffs for going to school every day got the lowest weighted mean both for teachers and administrators with a mean of 2.64 and 2.74 which was verbally described as moderately agree. Overall, teachers got a final weighted mean of 3.03 which verbally described as moderately agree, while administrators got a final weighted mean of 3.07 which also verbally described as moderately agree. This indicates that teachers and administrators have the same perception on teachers' performance.

Table 5 shows the data in terms of motivation of teachers. Data shows that the statement refers to students have good attitude towards learning got the highest weighted mean of 4.00 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to students got good grade in new normal, and students and their parent shows appreciation got the lowest weighted mean of 3.33 which verbally described as moderately agree. This indicates that having a good grade is one of the motivations of the teachers to strive hard, while appreciation was considered least. Thus, students and parents need to show appreciation to teacher's hard work.

Table 5. Motivational

MOTIVATIONAL	Teachers	
	Mean	VD
Students have good attitude towards learning	4.00	A
Students got good grade in new normal	3.33	MA
Students and their parent shows appreciation	3.33	MA
Administrator shows their appreciation and rewards my good work.	3.67	A
School has good facilities and I have my own class room.	3.38	MA
Good working environment	3.54	A
I get sufficient and constructive feedback from my co-teachers and administrator	3.67	A
Grand Mean	3.56	A

Table 6. Demotivational

DEMOTIVATIONAL	Teachers		Administrator	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
School does not have good policy and administration supports	3.33	MA	3.15	MA
There is lack of positive feedback	3.63	A	3.10	MA
I have lack of time for family and home	3.15	MA	3.55	MA
Working hours are odd	3.12	MA	3.55	MA
Low salary/pay	3.63	A	3.15	MA
There are lack of training and development	3.12	MA	3.42	A
There are lack of promotion opportunity	3.67	A	3.25	A
Grand Mean	3.38	MA	3.31	MA

Table 6 shows the data in terms of demotivation of teachers. Data shows that the statement refers to there are lack of promotion opportunity got the highest weighted mean of 3.67 which verbally described as agree, while the statement refers to there are lack of training and development got the lowest weighted mean of 3.12 which verbally described as moderately agree. This indicates that lack of promotion made the teachers demotivated.

Table 7. Test of Significant Difference

Sources	Motivation	MEAN	p-value	Decision
Teachers		3.03	0.903965	Not Significant
Administrators	Preparation	2.99		
	Distribution	3.07 2.81	0.31327	Not Significant
	Retrieval	2.83 2.93	0.672692	Not Significant
	Performance	3.03 3.07	0.76449	Not Significant

The Table 7 described the significant differences of the teachers and administrators of teacher's motivation in the new normal. Data shows that p value is greater than alpha 0.05, this indicates that there is enough evidence to prove that teachers and administrators do not differ much on its level of perception on teachers' motivation.

Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted that there is no significant difference on the respondent groups perception.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, data shows that both respondent groups have perceived that teacher need a help in terms of preparation, distribution and retrieval of modules in this new normal of education. The data also suggests that teachers need physical support in fulfilling their job. Results also suggest that there is a need an immediate support for teachers to cater the needs of students and parents, such as time allowance in module distribution and retrieval. Moreover, findings shows that there is no significant difference on teachers and administrators' perception on teachers' motivation/ need in this new normal.

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